

The complexes $[\text{CrL}_2(\text{NCS})_2]$ ($\text{LH}=\text{Hsal}$ or HOap) and $[\text{Cr}(\text{HOap})(\text{Oap})(\text{NCS})_2]$ display ν_{CO} band at $1640-1615\text{ cm}^{-1}$ whereas the free ligand displays this band in the region $1650-1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A marked shift in the ν_{CO} vibration suggests the bonding of ketonic oxygen to metal atom⁶. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ of phenolic group is shifted to higher wave number (1325 for Hsal and 1330 cm^{-1} for HOap complexes) from free ligand (1170 and 1190 cm^{-1}) which suggest the coordination of deprotonated phenolic oxygen to chromium(III)⁶. The NH stretch of anthranilate group in $[\text{Cr}(\text{antr})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is not resolved and is observed as a broad band at $3300-3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to water molecule. However, NH_2 bending band is located at 1612 cm^{-1} which is lower than bending band 1634 cm^{-1} of free ligand, indicating the coordination of amino group nitrogen to the metal atom. The carboxyl group $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ of anthranilate group is observed at 1570 and 1345 cm^{-1} as a broad band. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ of free anthranilic acid is observed at 1520 and 1410 cm^{-1} . The red-shift of ν_{as} and blue-shift in $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ vibrations suggest the unidentate nature of carboxylate group to metal atom⁷. The absence of ν_{OH} band and red-shift of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibration (1275 cm^{-1}) of HOxin in $[\text{Cr}(\text{Oxin})_2(\text{NCS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (free ligand displays $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and 1100 cm^{-1})^{6,7} suggest the deprotonation and bonding of phenolic oxygen to metal. The ν_{CN} band of HOxin (1575 cm^{-1}) also shifts to higher frequency (1600 cm^{-1}) indicating the coordination of pyridine nitrogen to metal atom⁶. The ir spectra of the complexes could not be recorded in far-infrared region therefore, nothing could be said about M-L vibration.

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Copper(II) Complexes of 2-Alkoxy-4-amino/imino-6,7-diphenyl-7-oxo-1,3,5-triaza-1,3,5-heptatriene and 2,11-Dialkoxy-4,9-diamino/imino-6,7-diphenyl-1,3,5,8,10,12-hexaza-1,3,5,7,9,11-dodecahexene

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BIGUANIDES and *O*-alkylamidinoisourea have almost similar characteristics¹. Both of them are strong field ligands and can form complexes with metal ions in higher oxidation states². Their metal complexes exhibit pseudo-aromatic character³. The formation of Schiff bases with these ligands are expected to influence the stability and bonding parameters. The cryomagnetic and spectral studies of one such series of Schiff bases derived from biguanide and salicylaldehyde have been reported⁴. We have also reported⁵ copper(II) complexes with Schiff bases derived from *O*-alkylamidinoisourea and salicylaldehyde. The results of such investigation in which bridging groups have been introduced connecting two *O*-alkylamidinoisourea pertain to the present study.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E. Merck grade. Solvents were used as such.

Our attempt to isolate the ligand from the starting materials was futile. Hence the complexes were prepared *in situ* by template method by the reaction of cyanoguanidine, benzoin/benzil in the presence of the copper(II) salts.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{ADTH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2\text{Cl}_2$: A mixture of cyanoguanidine (2 mmol) and benzoin (2 mmol) dissolved in methanol, was refluxed till all cyanoguanidine went into solution. A methanolic solution of $\text{CuCl}_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 mmol) and sodium acetate was added to it and the solution was refluxed for 2 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 . Other complexes were prepared by using different copper(II) salts and appropriate alcohols.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{DDHD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: A mixture of cyanoguanidine (2 mmol) and benzil (1 mmol) dissolved in methanol, was refluxed till all cyanoguanidine

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd	Colour	M p °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)*					μ_{eff} B M	ξ
			M	N*	C	H	Cl		
[Cu(DMDHD)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Colour	>250	10 94 (11 01)	19 38 (19 42)	41 51 (41 63)	4 44 (4 50)	12 24 (12 31)	1 75	2 014
[Cu(DMDHD)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Pink	>250	10 21 (10 08)	22 29 (22 23)	38 23 (38 12)	4 21 (4 13)	—	1 78	2 019
[Cu(DEDHD)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Red	>250	10 43 (10 51)	18 48 (18 52)	43 54 (43 67)	4 87 (4 96)	11 62 (11 74)	1 81	2 018
[Cu(DEDHD)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Rose red	>250	9 77 (9 65)	21 21 (21 19)	40 19 (40 15)	4.51 (4 56)	—	1 76	2 013
[Cu(MDTH)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Pink	>250	14 72 (14 33)	12 59 (12 62)	46 11 (46 04)	4 55 (4 51)	8 14 (8 01)	1 62	2 025
[Cu(MDTH)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Rose	>250	13 31 (13 52)	14 88 (14 92)	43 37 (43 45)	4 31 (4 25)	—	1 61	2 021
[Cu(EDTH)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Rose	>250	13 76 (13 89)	12 39 (12 25)	47 21 (47 26)	4 78 (4 81)	4 68 (4 76)	1 63	2 013
[Cu(EDTH)(H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Pink	>250	12 98 (13 13)	14 38 (14 47)	41 54 (41 61)	4 26 (4 23)	—	1 61	2 016

*Including nitrate nitrogen

went into solution. A methanolic solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O (1 mmol) and sodium acetate was added to it and the solution was refluxed for 2 h and then allowed to cool to room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and dried over fused CaCl₂. The filtrate on standing overnight yielded fresh crystals. Other complexes were prepared by using different copper(II) salts and different alcohols.

When similar type of the above reaction was carried out with nickel(II) and cobalt(II) salts, no complexes could be isolated.

Copper and nitrogen content of the complexes were estimated by standard methods. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy type balance. The analytical data and physical properties of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer, reflectance spectra (MgCO₃) on a Cary 2390 spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a Varian E-4 spectrometer (100 KHz) at room temperature. A cylindrical quartz sample was used for the esr spectra of the powdered samples using picryl dihydrazide free radical as *g* marker in a dual channel cavity and the frequency was modulated with help of a frequency meter.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are highly stable at room temperature. They are attacked by acids and alkalis. Their high molar conductance values suggest them to be 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytes for benzoin and benzil derivative of the Schiff base respectively. The complexes are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents but highly soluble in DMF and DMSO. The complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) are not formed probably due to their preferred geometry.

Ir spectra: The ir spectra of the complexes are highly complicated. However, attempts have been

made to identify some important bands which furnish informations regarding the mode of bonding in the complexes. The spectra of the complexes of the present study are compared with the spectra of similar type of complexes having an identical ligand moiety⁶.

In the higher frequency region of the spectra, all the complexes exhibit a strong and broad band at 3 450–3 100 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the combined mode of vibration of ν_{OH} , ν_{NH} and ν_{NH_2} . The broadness of the band is perhaps due to the presence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The absence of any band above $\sim 1 660$ cm⁻¹ indicate absence of carbonyl group and formation of azomethine group. The appearance of sharp bands at $\sim 1 645$ cm⁻¹ confirm the presence of water. The nature of the water molecules seems to be coordinated, which is supported by thermal analyses. Further, strong bands with sharp peaks observed in the spectra of the complexes at $\sim 1 010$ and ~ 860 cm⁻¹ are due to wagging and twisting mode of vibration of water molecules⁷. A weak band at $\sim 1 625$ cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. The peaks at $\sim 1 025$ and $1 220$ cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_a (C–O–R) and ν_{as} (C–O–R) modes respectively. In addition, the complexes of ADTH display some additional bands. A bidentate bridging oxo-group absorbs generally at a comparatively higher frequency ($\sim 1 550$ cm⁻¹). Hence the strong band at $\sim 1 540$ cm⁻¹ in the spectra of ADTH complexes can be assigned to the presence of an oxo-bridge⁸.

The coordination of NO₃⁻ group is generally ascertained by the appearance of bands⁹ at $\sim 1 200$ and $1 020$ cm⁻¹. Since no such bands have been observed in the metal complexes, it may be concluded that the anionic groups are not coordinated, a fact already observed from the conductance data.

Electronic and magnetic properties: The magnetic moments of ADTH complexes are low (1.58–1.51 B.M.) at room temperature which is perhaps due to

the orbital quenching with the formation of an oxo-bridge of the type¹⁰, $\text{Cu} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{Cu}$. But the complexes of DDHD show normal magnetic moments (1.73–1.82 B.M.) corresponding to the spin-only value.

The electronic spectra of the complexes are broad with a center at ~ 710 nm. This approximates to the distorted octahedral configuration¹² around copper(II) ion.

Thermal analyses: The thermograms of all the complexes exhibit almost an identical pattern. In all the complexes there is no mass loss upto 200° suggesting the absence of lattice water¹². The first weight-loss at $\sim 220^\circ$ in a single step is supported by an exothermic peak at the same temperature in the DTA thermogram. The weight-loss corresponds to the loss of two water molecules (7.52% against the calculated value of 7.57%) and the exothermic peak in the DTA curve indicate bond-breaking. Such type of thermal behaviour is exhibited by coordinated water molecules¹³. After 220° , the thermogram is horizontal upto 240° . Further decomposition proceeds slowly from $\sim 250^\circ$ with a final residue at $\sim 780^\circ$. The second step corresponds to the thermal decomposition of the organic constituents of the complex and the final residue to the metal oxide. The thermal stability of the complexes with respect to the substituents follow the order, $\text{Me} < \text{Et} < \text{Pr} < \text{i-Pr}$ etc.

Esr spectra: The esr spectra of the polycrystalline ADTH and DDHD complexes exhibit a single exchange narrowed line at g_{av} 2.08 with a peak-to-peak separation of about 110 gauss. The esr spectra of the complexes are comparable with that of the copper(II) complexes of *O*-alkylamidinoisourea and biguanides¹⁴. The proposed structure suggests an axial symmetry. However, random distribution of axes in the samples might have led to the observation of esr signal at an average g value.

Based on the above observations the structures may be proposed for the complexes.

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Polydentate Schiff Base Ligand Complexes of Transition Metals

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CONDENSATION of bis(acetylaceton)ethylenediamine with benzoylhydrazide led to the synthesis of a new potentially pentadentate ligand bis-